

A qualitative and multicriteria assessment of scientists: a perspective based on a case study of INRAE, France

Abstract: Psychosociology theories indicate that individual evaluation is part of the recognition of professional activities. Following Christophe Dejours conclusions, this recognition is shaped by two complementary judgments: the “utility” judgment given by the hierarchy and the “beauty” judgment given by the peers. The aim of this paper is to explain how at INRAE individual assessment of scientists is operated, following a qualitative and multicriteria-based process by peers, that provides congrats and advices to the assessed scientists (the “beauty” judgment). We explain as well how INRAE regularly adapts this process to the evolution of research practices, such as interdisciplinarity or open science, since assessment requires to be in phase with how research activities are performed.

Keywords: multicriteria assessment, open science, peers, qualitative evaluation, research assessment

Why an assessment of scientists?

Scientists' life is punctuated by different types of evaluations: during recruitment, promotions, calls for projects and throughout the career.

In France, civil-servant scientist (with permanent position) assessment is mandatory and legislated by decree 83-1260 (30th December 1983¹) setting the statutory rules common to the French research organisations. This obligation is an opportunity to think a mean for making assessment by peers useful to both the concerned scientist and the research organization. This articles concerns the regular assessment throughout the career and thus does not deal with promotions.

In France, and in other countries as well, there are mainly two types of institutions for research and higher education: research institutes (devoted mainly on research) and universities (with a shared goal of high education and research). French universities recruit scientists both on their scientific skills and their teaching specialities. In terms of assessment, there is no regular assessment of scientists at French universities (except for promotion). In French research institutes such as INRAE (French national research institute for agriculture, food and environment) scientists are hired based on their scientific expertise, their research skills and projects. At INRAE, assessment occurs every two years, independently of promotions and most of other French research institutes do the same.

How can we assess “work”? The word « work » has several meanings such as « labour » and « artwork ». Evaluation has to take into account these two senses of work as « executing a task » and « creating something new ». Following the theories of Christophe Dejours (2003), “work” itself (in its two meanings) cannot be assessed: only the *results* of the work are visible and accessible to evaluation. Assessment of the results of the work can be and is commonly performed by measuring, counting, consisting on a quantitative approach. All efforts, tricks and intelligence put in reaching prescribed objectives represent the very essence of work and are often not visible to the evaluator. The real “work” defined by Christophe Dejours must be assessed through qualitative criteria, the ones based on “telling”, “relating”, “explaining”, “clarifying”, all verbs that tell a “story”. Consequently, the persons who are the more appropriate to identify and assess the “work” in the sense of Dejours are peers: they perform the same job, they know the rules, they face similar difficulties and themselves create new tricks to reach their objectives.

Why peer-assessment of scientists work is important and necessary? Back to theory in sociology,

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<http://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000000316777&fastPos=1&fastReqId=1906599245&categorieLien=cid&oldAction=rechTexte>

recognition is essential for well-being at work, for each worker, including scientists. Christophe Dejours again indicates that recognition involves two kinds of judgments: the “utility” judgment and the “beauty” judgment. They are complementary and necessary. The first one is given by the hierarchy, indicating that activities and work of the worker are useful for the organisation; this gives a meaning to the work performed by the worker. The second one is given by peers, people who know the work simply because they do the same job. Peers are thus the only ones who understand and consider the difficulties encountered by the assessed person; they can even catch hidden parts of the work developed to reach the objectives, in addition to the usual prescriptions.

These assessments proposed by Christophe Dejours are general and not specific for assessment of scientist work. But this represents a context, a frame in which INRAE proposes an assessment procedure to approach the best as possible a qualitative assessment of scientists: an evaluation performed by peers in a collegial manner, aiming at giving advices (and not penalties or rewards), and taking into account a large diversity of missions and activities corresponding to personal and professional trajectories. To our knowledge, INRAE is unique (among other French research institutes and universities) in referring to this theory.

The aim of individual assessment is to judge the work, not the person. In practice, the peers at INRAE refers to the report, trying to i) understand the situation of the person in the organization (team, lab, institute...) and ii) to focus on the activities and realizations, on the substance of what is written rather than the number of publications and iii) to analyse the person’s hintsight on her or his work. Those elements are dicussed between the members of the committee (see below) and then, a message is delivered by the committee towards the evaluated scientist which consists in their “beauty judgment”.

Quantitative versus qualitative assessment

Most of assessment methods applied by organisations (and not only by research organisations but also by funders) have been or are still centred on quantitative criteria which are useful for evaluating the results of the work, but not the work itself. Counting achievements (such as publications for scientists) is easy but is now considered as imperfect and even unfair: how to take into account the fact that some achievements (e. g. publications) are much easier to produce than others, depending on the discipline and the driven hypotheses? One of the solutions to quantify production in research is (was) the impact factor of the journal where the articles are published. This is based on the idea that because it is harder to publish in a high-ranked journal, the work is better than if published in a low-ranked journal. Nowadays, and since only a few years, these quantitative parameters (number of publications, impact factor, H index, quartile rank of the journal, ...) are less in used and even banned from several

organisations (DORA, the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment²), because a simple ranking confers a restrictive view of the work. This restrictive view is linked to the fact that those parameters only measure the result of the work, i. e. the quantitative objectives. They do not reflect how the scientist organises his/her ideas, tackles the aim of the study, faces the difficulties or novelties he/she encounters. None of the aspects on the capacities of the person to adapt to professional situations, to search and find solutions, to play with unpredictable results are detected by quantitative parameters. Those capacities represent the extended vision of the “real work”, to face the resistance of the real, to paraphrase Christophe Dejours. In some instances, this “real work” could be hidden, because it does not follow the canonical ways (and may even break the rules), or because the situation forces the worker to take risks (and defying the odds). In research, the hidden work could correspond to all the trials that failed, or all the negative results (experiment that did not failed but which did not consolidate the starting hypothesis). If nothing is mentioned about those “failures”, than it hides all efforts that took times and that - in a sense - allowed to reach the objective by exploring all possibilities to make new knowledge arising. In terms of assessment, it is important to leave space to the scientist to tell, explain all these elements that contain all the ways and means used to reach the scientific objectives (which then could be translated into a publication for instance).

The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)³ campaigns for an “assessment of research, researchers and research organisations that recognises the diverse outputs, practices and activities that maximise the quality and impact of research. This requires basing assessment primarily on qualitative judgement, for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators”. This is a very important position statement signed by hundreds of European universities and institutions (such as INRAE) that fights the current and dominant paradigm of quantitative assessment of research. To our opinion, the desire for a paradigm shift started by bottom-up initiatives (DORA, Leiden Manifesto⁴...), followed by international European and national top-down decisions, applied again through bottom-up initiatives such as Peer Community In (PCI)⁵.with the common view to move towards a qualitative assessment.

The current paradigm of quantitative assessment in research started in the 1980's and was based on the new public management theory which highlights indicators, in order to define excellence of research. Thus, based on bibliometric approaches, it became easy for non-scientist people (such as politics, administrative managers) to rank, to compare people and organizations based on a common vocabulary of indicators. Gingras (1996) clearly relates what is bibliometry applied to research: he identified negative (mostly when applied to individual assessment) as well as positive aspects of it (to follow

² <https://sfdora.org/read/>

³ <https://coara.eu/> COARA: Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment

⁴ <http://www.leidenmanifesto.org/>

⁵ <https://peercommunityin.org/>

temporal dynamics of science). Thus, indicators could be useful for specific situations and are still central in assessment procedures.

Indicators are very useful for ranking. A recent open discussion at DORA[‡] centered on the putative negative consequences of rankings in evaluation practices, in relation with a capitalist approach of research activities. Krystian Szadkowski has linked the capitalist economy to the way science works (liberalism as a frame for competing for funding research) and to the ranking and prestige of institutions and researchers: everything is intertwined. Indeed, there are several examples around the world of governmental wills to “profitable” research, meaning entering the “value for money” in research assessment (e.g. Martin 2011 in England, Gingras and Khelifaoui 2021 for the French medical research). However, evaluation could represent a lever to start untangling the knot. Ranking is easy, everywhere, partner of capitalist economy, and father of quantitative assessment. This is detrimental to public research and several initiatives act to reasoned out the use of ranking. We will not here develop the issue of international rankings of universities and research insitutions (since our aim is to put in perspective individual scientist assessment). We can however mention the “More Than Our Ranks” (MTOR) initiative⁷ (<https://inorms.net/more-than-our-rank/>) in the frame of the International Network of Research Management Societies (INFORMS) which aims at providing institutions with tools for assessing all their activities independently of rankings.

Peers for a qualitative assessment scientists work

The challenge today for research organisations, for their managers and for the scientists is to have access to an assessment method more appropriate than a strictly quantitative one. The aim is to grasp the « hidden » activities (success, but also difficulties, failures, strategies to overcome problems) of researchers that represent the real work (and not only the results of the work). This is the role and responsibilities of peers, who are central to this process.

Following the decree of 1983, INRAE developed the process of regular scientist assesement. Initially, the elements of evaluation were mainly a report and list of productions analysed by committees (see below) which sent a message to the scientist. The scheme is still used today; however, the content and structure of the report and productions have changed and several items as been developped (see below). One first major re-orientation occurred when France decided to create a National division for research organization assesements in 2006 (the so-called AERES, which became the HCERES⁸): INRAE decided then to work on adapted criteria for research institutes based on finalized objectives. and this was the first time when multicriteria approach of assessment of scientists appeared, and is still used

⁶ <https://sfdora.org/2023/06/07/to-rank-not-to-rank-or-to-rank-responsibly/>

⁷ <https://inorms.net/more-than-our-rank/>

⁸ <https://www.hceres.fr/en>

today (see below). This was crucial to follow the evolution of the different activities of a scientist at INRAE. Today there are still challenges: integrating assessment of open science practices, of interdisciplinarity, of scientific integrity and of qualitative assessment, one of the aims of this perspective.

Nowadays at INRAE, individual assessment of scientists is performed by groups of peers called “Specialized Scientific Commissions” (SSC), organized by disciplines or groups of disciplines. The 13 SSC cover all the types of disciplines present at INRAE (**Table 1**), and each INRAE scientist selects the SSC which corresponds the best to her/his activities. Each of the 13 INRAE SSC is a group of 20-24 scientists nominated or elected for four years - half of them not belonging to INRAE - and headed by a president who is external to INRAE. Within a committee, there are representatives of different categories of groups: the gender balance is respected, as well as the age category, trying to balance “junior” and “senior” assessors in order to capitalise on their different views. Each of the SSC follows the precise guidelines given by INRAE since several years (Direction de l’Evaluation, 2023). When peers meet to discuss on the different dossiers, a representative of the Evaluation Department is present to be guarantor of the process, to ensure proper operation according to SSC rules, in order in particular to ban all mis-use of quantitative criteria and to respect the 25 criteria of discrimination prohibited by the French law (article 225-1 of the penal code, 2022).

Table 1: List of the 13 INRAE Specialized Scientific Commissions (SSC). Alphabetical order.

Agronomy, Livestock and Forest
Animal Biology
Ecology, Population biology and ecosystems dynamics
Economics, Sociology and Management science
Environmental sciences: earth, water and atmosphere
Interactions between Pests, Symbionts or Commensals with their Hosts
Mathematics, Informatics, Digital sciences, Artificial intelligence and Robotics
Microbiology, Microbial ecosystems, Agri-food systems, Biotechnology
Nutrition and Toxicology
Plant and Animal Genetics
Plant Integrative Biology
Research support and management
Science and food, materials and bio-based products engineering, Materials, Residual Resources

Peers (either internal or external to INRAE) are not retributed for their work. INRAE considers that this is part of the “expertise” criteria (see below) to participate to peer evaluation in the SSC. The average

cost of one SSC per year is approximately 8000 euros for reimbursement, based on 3 to 4 days of meeting per SSC, with no interview (see below, conclusions) and for assessing approx. 700 scientists per year.

The SSC produce sovereign assessments, independently of INRAE hierarchy. SSC give advices which are collegially discussed. Specific referees – chosen among the members of the SSC - are appointed for each evaluated scientist but remains unknown for him/her, and this confidentiality is important since the judgment of “beauty” is thus given by a community of peers, and not by only one peer, in order to strengthen the value and the significance of the assessment. The output of this process is a personal and dedicated “beauty” judgment emitted through a written message every two or three years by peers of the discipline towards the evaluated INRAE scientists.

An advice-based assessment

As stated above, scientist assessment is based on the “beauty” judgment made by peers. The aim for INRAE is not to punish or reward, but to give advices in a humanelly manner and with good will. The advice is usually balanced between congratulations on the positive aspects evaluated by the peers, and opinions on the choices that has been made by the scientist (for instance on methods), the dynamics and relevance of the research, or orientation that could be followed (for instance in terms of collaboration). This general advice concerns the trajectory of the evaluated scientists and may differ between a junior an a senior scientist. As an exemple, the message could contain this kind of the following elements and sentences: a sentence of context “You work on the effect of...”, “You are involved in projects aiming at...”; than a series of sentences that congratulate activites (specific results, or/and management of an important project, or/and involvement in education if it is the case, and/or more specific activities (open science,...)). The last series of sentences often point some advice or elements of discussion concerning the near future, orientation of the project, trajectory of the future career... When the situation shows some elements of degradation (see below), this can be mentioned carefully in the message: “The committee identified a critical issue concerning your publications since you did not publish since...”, or “Concerning the relationship within your group which seems to limit your possibility to...”, “In that context, the committee will inform your hierarchy in order to help you in resolving this issue”. A long time is taken to write those messages in order to be sure that there is no ambiguity and to limit possible mis-interpretation by the assessed scientist when reading it. One particular element taken into account is the coherence of their work with the global strategy of INRAE, even if this specific point, from a theoretical point of view is more an “utility” judgement. Since the commissions work independently and sovereignly on their judgment of “beauty”, there is no direct link with the judgment of “utility” given by the hierarchy. The latter is given by laboratory directors or senior managers: the evaluated researcher must include the opinion of his/her laboratory director in his/her file, after a personal interview. This opinion and interview constitute a “utility” judgment. In other words, during the whole assessment process, the researcher receives the two opinions he/she needs to gain recognition for his work (from

the peers and from the hierarchy, but the opinions are given independently. However, there are indirect links, since i) the hierarchy receives the messages delivered by the commissions to the researchers and ii) the commissions contact the hierarchy in the case of difficulties encountered by the researchers (see below).

By reading the whole file written by the evaluated scientist, and since it is highly recommended to write it in a “telling story” mode, the peers can detect in some cases different types of difficulties the evaluated person might encountered, and transmit it to the hierarchy. Either because the evaluated person relates a difficult situation in the document, or because the SSC members detect a lack of dynamics or motivation. This action enables the hierarchy to do what is needed (e. g. contacting the scientist, the head of the lab,...) with the help of professional human resources people at INRAE to understand and help the person and the lab to disentangle the situation and to make it resolved as far as it is feasible. In **Table 2**, we give an example of types of such situations detected in 2020 (60 concerned scientists) and 2021 (74 concerned scientists) for a total of 1454 assessed scientists. Most of the situations (78%) are easily resolved in a few months: a simple discussion between the scientist and her/his hierarchy is sufficient to clarify the issue and resolve it. For other cases, both parties agree that a change is necessary and different solutions are examined, such as a change of team or laboratory, or even missions. It may take a year or even more. And in a very few cases, the situation is very degraded (for any reason) and a deep analysis is performed, with several professional of human resources management.

Table 2: Types of difficulties identified by the peers, for 2020 et 2021. This corresponds to 105 different assessments (scientists). For each scientist, the difficulty might fit with different types.

Type	Junior scientists	Senior scientist	Total
Weak project	50	5	55
Lack of autonomy, motivation, dynamism...	14	1	15
Level of activity (lack of scientific output, dispersed activities...)	37	2	39
Working environment, conflicts, medical issue, overwork...	49	17	66
Non-delivered document or incomplete records	7	4	11

During the discussion between members of the committees, it can happen that different views on a specific case are expressed. There is no specific procedures to manage those discussions, but this is when the role of the president of the committee is important: his/her personality and ability to establish a climate of listening trust combined with benevolence helps to manage any subsequent conflicts and to take consensual decisions. If an un-resolved conflict occurs between members of a committee (this happened to our knowledge only once during the last five years) then the Evaluation Department acts as

mediator between the concerned appraisers.

In conclusion, the role of peers is essential to help scientists having a recognition via a “beauty” judgement, and to anticipate difficulties in order in most cases to be able to prevent a situation from escalating. We pay particular attention to junior scientists during their first years at INRAE: this consists on three assessments during the five years following their recruitment, in order to help them to stabilize their project and first achievements.

A multicriteria assessment

There are several reasons for taking into account different criteria during scientist assessment. First, INRAE is a research institute that combines basic and applied approaches in order to get finalized objectives towards the society; this encompasses several kinds of disciplines and expertises that each requires specific criteria (an agronomist working with farmers towards a molecular biologist at the bench). Second, missions of scientists are not limited to the production of knowledge but include expertise, education and management. Third, missions of scientists change during the career and senior scientists tend to get more involved in management.

In the mid-2000s, INRA and Irstea (the two founding organizations of INRAE) created and participated to the inter-institutional working group on the evaluation of the finalized research called EREFIN (“Evaluation de la REcherche FINalisée” which stands in French for “Assessment of Finalized Research”). The aim was to promote a comprehensive assessment enlarging the single assessment of producing and disseminating new knowledge to the other missions mentioned above such as expertise, training, contribution to scientific culture... This resulted in a production of tools allowing a topology of possible activities, a list of possible products and descriptors, as well as criteria for assessment (EREFIN 2011). Today, this consists on tools that are still largely used in different organizations and assessments in France.

At INRAE, and based on EREFIN, we propose the scientists to declare their involvement in the different expected activities in four main types (**Figure 1**):

- Production of knowledge.
- Expertise and knowledge mobilization.
- Training through research, initial and continuing training.
- Animation or direction of institutional groups, major instruments, resources, programs or networks.

This list is a representation of the different possible areas of actions, submitted to the “beauty” judgment of the peers in the SSC; it is not expected that a given scientist “ticks” all of these activities. As a

consequence, the peers will not criticize a scientist for not being active in the four activities. Peers have thus to evaluate how the scientist manages her/his different activities and if this is consistent with her/his objectives and stage in her/his career. Assessment at INRAE aims - as well - at examining the trajectory of scientists since we do not expect the same distribution of time among the four different main types between a junior and a senior scientist. Depending on age, experience, trajectory, scientific domain, researchers may sign in at different levels these four main types (**Figure 2**).

Figure 1: description of the four main types of activities at INRAE that scientists under assessment can mention and develop in their report.

Figure 2: example of repartition of the activities of junior and senior INRAE scientists. CRCN: Chargé de Recherche Classe Normale (first degree of scientist recruitment at INRAE). DREX: Directeur de recherche classe Exceptionnelle (last degree of promotion at INRAE). Based on 4989 responses of scientists on a period of 2015-2021 years.

Evolution of qualitative assessment criteria

Qualitative assessment by SSC members is based on a frame and guidelines given to the scientist to drive the writing towards a “story telling mode” centred on i) facts and achievements, and ii) a reflexive analysis of the activity (success, failure, difficulties...) (Direction de l’Evaluation, 2023).

Assessment based only on (inappropriate) quantitative metrics appears to be the easiest way for an automatic or administrative assessment by non-pairs, by people unable to analyse the real quality of work and of products of work. There are several exemples of mis-adaption of quantitative indicators for research assessment of individuals. One of it refers to impact factors and number of citations which poorly correlate with basic trends expected for three main tested items representative of a good quality research: statistics, value of declared data, and replicability (Dougherty and Horne 2022). Generalising the switch of assessment from quantitative metrics to a qualitative approach might however requires the definition and implementation of “qualitative indicators” In 2019, Wouters et al. (2019) proposed a framework with about 150 indicators and evaluated their relevance for different kinds of assessments (infrastructures, research and funding organisations, individual researcher activity, career progression and recruitment). This approach helps in defining qualitative indicators but the temptation could be to qualitatively assess with a too long list of indicators, and to eventually fall back into the paradox of a quantitative approach for a qualitative assessment. Subjectivity in qualitative approaches is well known

(mainly for studies in humanities such as sociology) (Bumbuc 2016); the most important element is that everyone addressing qualitative assessment has to be aware when subjectivity acts and to correct this threats when assessing the quality of research. It is known that cross-checking analyses and sharing opinion on a situation (the so-called triangulation, Fichten & Dreier 2003) is a way to limit the negative effect of subjectivity. So i) indicators are necessary to limit the risk that subjectivity operating during qualitative assessment, and ii) the use a multicriteria approach - as performed at INRAE - might limit this risk by buffering each criteria to - at the end - define the profile of each scientist by the distribution of her/his types of activities.

For an organization such as INRAE, qualitative assessment has to take into account possible new orientations of research practices. Recently, INRAE decided to strengthen activities and visibility on different aspects that are developed below : expertise, partnership, interdisciplinarity and open science.

Expertise and support for public policies: the aim of expertise is to make available to actors responsible for public policies (ministries, agencies, local authorities, European and international institutions, universities etc.), scientific and technical knowledge, tools and methods that help inform, design, implement and evaluate public policies. At INRAE, these activities take various forms: collective scientific expertise, prospective, studies and research for and on public policies, training, working groups, participation in bodies of public actors, design and management of observatories or databases... All these aspects are listed in the guidelines provided to the scientists who are invited to describe those activities in their assessment files. Peers will check how these expertise activities suit with the three other types of activities, and how they are coherent with the personal trajectory of the assessed scientist, how they were performed with which outputs and if they are disseminated to the correct audience.

Research in partnership with a view to contribute to all forms of innovation: the innovations are the result of diversified partnerships between research or training establishments, technical centers or technical agricultural and agro-industrial institutes, competitiveness clusters, public and private economic actors, civil society actors; this aims at favoring the co-construction of the value creation process between all the actors of the project. INRAE defends the concept of diversity of innovations which means research may innovate for economic, political, environmental, societal or health issues. Being partner is to produce with others outputs that are enriched and different from what would have been produced alone. It is therefore essential in terms of assessment that the researcher partnership approach is made explicit in terms of co-design, co-construction and co-realization, on long-term programs, punctuated by more targeted projects, partnership that asks and answers questions of original and useful research.

Practices of interdisciplinarity: by definition, a partnership aims to create novelty, to do more together, by combining differences, ideas, skills, expertise and resources. “Collaborating” therefore implies working with people who are sometimes from different scientific backgrounds. The success of an interdisciplinary partnership implies the ability to dialogue between people from different disciplines. Thus, whether the partnership is academic, private, public or / and citizen, at the national level or by mixing nationalities, interdisciplinarity must be set in motion positively in the process of co-construction and co-realization. Taking into account interdisciplinarity in the assessment process is necessary in order to recognize the cost linked to this interdisciplinary effort and to focus, in this context, on the quality of the questioning of research and the relevance of this strategy. Practising interdisciplinarity, in terms of assessment can be seen as a penalty since the professional identity of the person is not straightforward and could be claimed by belonging to different social groups (Negro and Leung 2013). A recent study analysed more deeply this thread and showed that interdisciplinarity is penalized because of conforing social boundaries (Fini et al. 2023). At INRAE, because each SSC is centred on a given discipline, SSC might have difficulties to assess scientists who are at the interface of different disciplines: the peers of a given SSC might not be able to deliver an complete and adapted “beauty” judgment. As a consequence, INRAE gives the possibility to scientists to be assessed by two different SSC, covering the disciplines they use for their research (for instance mathematics and ecology). And thus, the evaluated scientist receives two complementary “beauty judgment” from each discipline. Here, we see that the social boundaries mentioned by Fini et al. (2023) do probably not act since this is the complementarity of the two judgment that occurs. However, this is still a proxy of assessment at the interface between two disciplines, since each SSC evaluates only one discipline and the real capacity to work at the interface is sometimes not well assessed.

Practices in open science: open science is a broad approach developed to improve reproductibility, transparency and robustness of research (Susi et al., 2022). Since several years, there is a strong international and European politics to strengthen open science practices mainly for publications (open access), data, code and computer programs, and citizen science. Most of the international scientific institutes and universities have signed different manifesto – such as DORA (<https://sfedora.org/read/>) and Leiden (Hicks et al; 2015) – and several countries (as well as the European Community) have define roadmaps to encourage scientists to follow these new practices. The main line of this implication is that the scientific content of an article is more important than the publication indicators, and that all data must be FAIR⁹ and well described by metadata.

Recently, in february 2022 during an OSEC (Open Science European Conference) in Paris (France), a large number of European universities, research organisations (including INRAE) and funders signed

⁹ FAIR data are data which meet principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability.

the “Paris Call on Research Assessment”¹⁰. The objective is to strengthen the common European vision on rewarding quality and the various impacts of research meeting the highest standards of ethics and integrity, on valuing the diversity of research activities, on rewarding not only the research outputs but also the appropriate conduct of research. Research organizations (including INRAE) have thus a well delimited frame to engage open science practices assessment. In that context, we performed a benchmark to analyse how different countries and organizations take into account open science practices. This benchmark was based on a corpus of twenty documents produced by different international organizations, states or universities (Bristol, UCL, Utrecht, ...) between 2015 and 2022 (**Table 3**).

Universities	
Utrecht University	Recognition and Rewards Vision - 2021
Delft University of Technology	Open Science Programme 2020-2024 Research and Education in the Open Era Evaluation 2021 & Work plan 2022 - 2021
University of Bristol	Academic Promotions Framework 2021-2022 - 2021
Universities Norway	NOR-CAM - A toolbox for recognition and rewards in academic careers - 2021
Maastricht University	Room for everyone’s talent at Maastricht University - 2020
University College London	UCL Academic Careers Framework - 2018
University Medical Center Utrecht	Guide for reviewers/evaluators that use the UMC Utrecht indicators for impact - 2016
Ghent University	Vision Statement For Evaluating Research At Ghent University - 2016
University of Glasgow	Academic Promotion Criteria
Others entities	
YUFE Alliance	Open Science Assessment and Incentives at the YUFE Alliance - 2022
LERU	A Pathway towards Multidimensional Academic Careers - 2022
VNSU, KNAW, NWO	Strategy Evaluation Protocol – 2021. Standard Evaluation Protocol - 2015
DORA, EUA, SPARC Europe	Reimagining Academic Career Assessment: Stories of innovation and change - 2021
TJNK, TSV	Good practice in researcher evaluation. Recommendation for the responsible evaluation of a researcher in finland - 2020
FOLEC	Towards A Transformation Of Scientific Research Assessment In Latin America And The Caribbean - 2020
VNSU, KNAW, NWO and ZonMw	Room for everyone's talent - 2019
European Commission	Evaluation of Research Careers fully acknowledging Open Science Practices - 2017

Table 3: Corpus used to compare and contrast scientist assessment at INRAE and other organizations. YUFE: Young Universities of the Future Europe. LERU: League of European Research Universities. KNAW, NWO and VSNU: association of universities in the Netherlands, which had already signed the DORA declaration. DORA: Declaration of San Francisco. EUA: European University Association. TJNK: Finish Committee for Public Information. TSV: Federation of Finnish Learned Societies. FOLEC: Latin American Forum on Research Assessment. ZonMw: The Netherlands Organisation for Health Research and Development.

¹⁰ <https://osec2022.eu/paris-call/>

Our benchmarking concerns mainly universities, national roadmaps and clusters of organisations (League of European Research Universities, European Commission...) that have broader objectives than INRAE with finalized objectives.

As a starting point, we checked how the four main activities used to structure the assessment of INRAE scientists (in brief, production of knowledge, expertise, training and management) cross referenced with criteria taken into account by other international organizations. First, the four INRAE activities cover all the types of activities detected in other organization assessment procedures in an open science context. In **Figure 3**, we show the correspondence between INRAE and other organization categories. There is a strong match, even if the vocabulary is different (for instance, as many organizations are universities, the term “Education” is more appropriate for them than ”Training”). There are terms that are not clearly mentioned in INRAE activities such as “Soft Skills” or “Leadership”: in our opinion, they refer to skills that affect the whole types of activities, and that are difficult to assess since they concern behaviour and abilities. And eventually, “Impact” assessment is proposed by other organizations but not directly by INRAE. INRAE has developed and applies tools (named ASIRPA¹¹) that define, describe and measure “impact” of research, but not at an individual level. This concerns economic, societal, political, environmental and health impacts of research on the mid- long-term based on projects or long-term research (Joly and Matt 2017; Joly et al. 2019). And INRAE considers that impact assessment cannot be appropriate to one person (the scientist) since an impact is systemic and include several actions and people.

Figure 3: comparison of categories used for assessment of research activities between INRAE (left) and

¹¹ https://www6.inrae.fr/asirpa_eng/

other organizations (right).

Based on the different axes (**Figure 3**), there is thus not a large discrepancy in the mode of research assessment between INRAE and other international organizations, and INRAE is one of the organisation that has set up procedures and criteria specific to open science assessment. Practically, we recommend the evaluated person to mention her/his possible involvement in open science by i) listing new products specific to bibliodiversity (e. g. preprints, data repositories...), ii) describing actions towards obtaining FAIR data, iii) describing her/his strategy in open science (e. g. choice of diamond or golden journals...), and if this is the case iv) explaining her/his personal implication or actions in open science such as participation in different open science initiative (e. g. Peer Community In, open peer reviews, processes for sharing data, citizen science...).

Open science practices question scientific integrity since new audiences are targeted, large dissemination of science results and production are promoted; as a consequence, a mis-use of these information might occur (social network, preprints considered as validated science...). This implies an enhanced vigilance for ethical and deontological views, transparency and traceability of research processes, and greater attention paid to research data, to their management, and whenever it is relevant, to their sharing. In terms of assessment of scientific integrity, INRAE gives the possibility to the scientists to express in their report how they step back their scientific integrity in general and more specifically facing open science practices.

Conclusions and tracks for the near future

The 20th July 2022, the “Agreement on reforming research assessment” was published by the European Commission (via Science Europe, the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment CoARA)¹², after a consultation of more than 350 organisations from 40 countries. This declaration implements 10 commitments that the signatories – including INRAE – undertake to follow and apply. Most of the commitments are already applied at INRAE for individual assessment of researchers: diversity of contributions, qualitative evaluation, abandon of inappropriate metrics, resources for reforming research assessment, multi- and adapted criteria, transparency of the processes. Of course, there is still improvement to make, such as extending the exchange of practices with our partners, communicating the progress made (this paper is part of it), and evaluating our practices. The following elements represent

¹² <https://www.scienceurope.org/our-resources/agreement-reforming-research-assessment/>

the evolution that we see to be important for INRAE in order to regularly take into account, even anticipate, evolutions of context and practices in the job of being a scientist.

Training for assessment. Emphasis on several missions like involvement in expertise and support for public policy and the generalisation of open science practices could be perceived by researchers as an unwelcome “top-down” imposition that increases the workload without any benefit. Moreover, in some disciplines (such as biology/medicine compared to mathematics), for structural or historical reasons, appropriation of such practices may be slow. Advocacy and training are thus essential for the researchers to understand the benefits for them. Such training is also important for the peer members of SSC in order to help them in applying an appropriate “beauty” judgment on these new practices.

A shared assessment between organizations. INRAE does not pretend to be the earliest in France or Europe to do so. But we are probably well engaged the qualitative assessment process based on the “beauty” judgment. Because of the top-down initiative by Europe and national ministries, INRAE acts in different national committees with other universities and research institutes. For instance, INRAE, CNRS and Inserm share common objectives for a better qualitative assessment based on international (DORA), European (CoARA) and national directives. This is truly necessary for a real evolution of assessment criteria: because of globalization of science, paradigm shift must be followed by a large majority of scientific organizations.

It is essential that all stakeholders involved in assessment share the common main objectives and use similar processes with appropriate indicators. Assessment of researchers occurs not only regularly by specific commissions such as INRAE SSC, but also at keypoints of their careers during their recruitment or promotion and the different juries have to apply the same general guidelines towards qualitative and multicriteria evaluation, including open science practices. And assessment of collective structures or projects must as well share a common base. In France, HCERES (the national agency for research and education assessment of organisations and laboratories) and ANR (national funding agency for research) do use multicriteria approach for assessment of organizations and projects, respectively, and recognize open science contributions, reducing the use of metrics such as H index and impact factor (the European ERC committees proceed the same)¹³. These are signs that assessment processes are changing and that a general common framework is shared at all assessment levels of researchers activities, funding and career development. Thus, the assessment procedure at INRAE i) follows what is usually performed in other research organizations but ii) is original in its way to center on a multicriteria approach and a

¹³ In French: <https://openscience.pasteur.fr/2022/01/17/le-hceres-signe-dora-et-fait-le-choix-dune-evaluation-multi-criteres-et-plus-qualitative/#626207478e82ce3af6eb/archives>, <https://anr.fr/fr/actualites-de-lanr/details/news/lanr-en-soutien-dune-science-ouverte/>, page 6 of <https://anr.fr/fileadmin/documents/2022/ANR-COP-2021-2025.pdf>

qualitative assessment adapted to a “beauty” judgment given by peers and iii) could be easily transferable to other institutes and universities (DORA Case study, 2023).

Impact of evaluation for scientists and INRAE. Individual assessment of scientists has two main outputs: one for INRAE in terms of identification of putative new scientific breakthroughs, and for the scientist in terms of professional trajectory and evolution. In short, these two outputs concerns the “evaluation of evaluation”, or the impact of evaluation. For the Institute, the evaluation reports drawn up by the researchers represent an unrivalled and very rich database from which quantitative and qualitative analyses could be carried out both to establish the state of play (strengths and weaknesses) at a given moment in the expression of research at INRAE, and to identify opportunities or risks for the years to come. INRAE is currently working on i) the questions to which the evaluation data could provide answers, and ii) the tools that will be used to extract and analyze the information. For the scientists, ASIRPA's ex-post tools (Joly and Matt 2017) could be adapted to analyze the impact of particular projects on researchers' careers, to help them gain perspective on their career path and impact, and thus clarify their professional future (scientific directions, mission orientation, etc.).

Towards assessment by interview. INRAE has today a roadmap that concerns several items such as integrating elements of scientific integrity on the report of the scientists. But it is still difficult to define criteria or indicators for it (Moher et al. 2020). One option could be to include an interview between the assessed scientist and the SSC; this might allow to question more deeply how the scientist faces scientific integrity on four main aspects: reliability, honesty, respect and responsibility. As well, interviews could include other aspects related to soft-skills which are more easy to appreciate by an oral exchange. And interviews will be an opportunity to deepen scientific discussions in order as well to help the scientists in their professional trajectories. Even if in the report scientists are invited to mention difficulties, failures they may have encountered, an interview is probably more adapted for them to explain these possible delicate situations. There are thus many advantages for considering interviews in the process of individual assessment. But today, there are at least two obstacles: first, the number of scientists at INRAE (approximately 2,500) is too high to organize such interviews, and second, interviews - by definition - will break the confidentiality rule of assessment. However, one intermediate track for setting these interviews could be to select a subset of assessed scientists based for example on a specific period in the career, and thus to accept that for these cases, confidentiality is broken.

Environmental impact. Evolution of assessment procedures and criteria is required since it follows the evolution of scientist missions and way of working. Professional environment is influencing the way scientists do their job. A simple example is the impact of the Sars-Cov-2 epidemic on in-house working and teleworking. But more deeply, the general environmental and societal contexts (not directly linked to science activities) may trigger new ways to consider the job of scientists: at INRAE, some scientists are aware of the impact of their activities on climate change and carbon footprint: they might orientate

their plans for experiments that are more energy-friendly, as well as reducing international traveling by air. These changes in practices might affect sizing of experiments and/or international collaborations. It is too early to see whether those putative changes will set up on a long term, but this is an example of how assessment procedures might evolve to take into considerations environmental impact of research activities.

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